

TABLE 1— β -SUBSTITUTED α -CYCLOPENTYLPROPIONIC ACIDS

Substituent	M.P./b.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found%		Requires%		2,4-DNP m.p.°C
				C	H	C	H	
1. 2,4-Dimethylbenzoyl	156	86.5	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O ₃	73.6	7.8	73.8	7.7	133
2. 2,5- " "	141	81.7	" "	73.5	7.7	73.8	7.7	165
3. 4- <i>t</i> -Butylbenzoyl	185	82.4	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₃	74.9	8.1	75.0	8.3	151
4. 4-Chlorobenzoyl	167	80.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₃ Cl	63.2	5.6	63.0	5.6	235
5. 2-(5,6,7,8-Tetrahydronaphthoyl)	232-5/9 mm	70.0	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₃	75.3	7.8	75.5	7.7	150
6. 2-Thienoyl	158	42.3	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ S	60.4	5.8	60.5	5.9	162-3

TABLE 2— γ -SUBSTITUTED α -CYCLOPENTYL-*n*-BUTYRIC ACIDS

Substituent	b.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found%		Requires%	
				C	H	C	H
1. 2,4-Dimethylphenyl	205/13 mm	86.2	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂	78.1	8.7	78.1	8.9
2. 2,5- " "	180/ 1 mm	87.8	C ₁₆ H ₂₂ O ₂	78.2	8.8	78.1	8.9
3. 4- <i>t</i> -Butylphenyl	170/ 6 mm	79.1	C ₁₆ H ₂₆ O ₂	78.6	9.4	78.8	9.5
4. 4-Chlorophenyl	195/ 5 mm	70.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ O ₂ Cl	66.3	6.6	66.5	6.7
5. 2-(5,6,7,8-Tetrahydronaphthyl)	165/ 5 mm	79.0	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₂	79.5	8.6	79.4	8.8
6. 2-Thienyl	140/ 2 mm	75.0	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ S	64.1	7.0	64.3	7.1

TABLE 3—7,8-SUBSTITUTED BENZO-*spiro*(4,5) DECAN-9-ONES

Substituent	b.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found%		Requires%		2,4-DNP m.p.°C
				C	H	C	H	
1. 1',3'-Dimethyl	145/0.5 mm	90.6	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O	84.1	8.7	84.2	8.8	149
2. 1',4'- " "	178/4.5 mm	84.9	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ O	84.0	8.7	84.2	8.8	120
3. 3'- <i>t</i> -Butyl	165/6 mm	72.2	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O	84.2	9.3	84.4	9.4	133
4. 3'-Chloro	135/4 mm	64.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ OCl	71.5	6.3	71.2	6.4	145
5. 2',3'-Tetramethylene	160/3 mm	78.7	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O	85.2	8.6	85.0	8.7	138

TABLE 4—7,8-SUBSTITUTED BENZO-*spiro*(4,5) DECANES

Substituent	b.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found%		Requires%	
				C	H	C	H
1. 1',3'-Dimethyl	130-1/3 mm	72.4	C ₁₆ H ₂₂	89.6	10.2	89.7	10.3
2. 1',4'- " "	135/6 mm	72.4	C ₁₆ H ₂₂	89.5	10.2	89.7	10.3
3. 3'- <i>t</i> -Butyl	140/4 mm	72.3	C ₁₈ H ₂₆	89.0	10.6	89.3	10.7
4. 3'-Chloro	145/3 mm	72.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ Cl	76.1	7.7	76.2	7.7
5. 2',3'-Tetramethylene	180/11 mm	70.8	C ₁₈ H ₂₄	90.2	10.1	90.0	10.0

TABLE 5

Name	b.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found%		Requires%		2,4-DNP m.p.°C
				C	H	C	H	
1. 7,8-Thienospiro(4,5)decan-9-one	155/8 mm	72.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ OS	69.7	6.5	69.9	6.8	149
2. 7,8-Thienospiro(4,5)decane	110/5 mm	67.7	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ S	74.8	8.0	75.0	8.3	—

the reaction mixture kept in an ice-salt bath for further 4 hr. The contents after keeping for 24 hr. at room temperature were heated in an oil bath (50°-60°) for 3 hr. and worked up in the customary manner. The pure title acid on crystallisation from benzene-petrol (60°-80°) in needles had m.p. 102° (4.5 g; 91.3%). (Found: C, 73.6; H, 7.5; equiv., 259.8. C₁₆H₂₀O₃ requires C, 73.8; H, 7.7% equiv., 260-monobasic).

Its 2,4-DNP on crystallisation from alcohol had m.p. 285°.

Other propionic acids are given in Table 1.

γ -(3,4-Dimethyl) phenyl- α -cyclopentyl-n-butyric acid, obtained by the reduction of the above acid (7.8 g) with amalgamated zinc (60 g) and conc. hydrochloric acid (120 ml) (55 hr) had b.p. 195°-7°/4 mm. (6.5 g; 88%). (Found : C, 78.2; H, 8.6; equiv., 245.7. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.1; H, 8.9%; equiv., 246-monobasic).

Other *n*-butyric acids similarly prepared are entered in Table 2.

7,8(2',3')-Dimethyl benzo spiro (4,5) decan-9-one, prepared by the cyclisation of the above acid (4.92 g) with PPA had b.p. 150°-1°/0.25 mm. (4.0 g; 87.7%). (Found : C, 84.0; H, 8.7. $C_{16}H_{20}O$ requires C, 84.2; H, 8.8%).

Its 2,4-DNP on crystallisation from alcohol had m.p. 216°. All the other *spiro* ketones prepared in an analogous manner are given in Tables 3 and 4.

7,8-(2',3'-Dimethyl) benzo spiro (4,5) decane.

Reduction of the above *spiro*-ketone (2.28 g) with amalgamated zinc (60 g), conc. hydrochloric acid (100 ml), toluene (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (2 ml) (60 hr) gave the title compound at 152°/1.5 mm. (1.6 g; 75%). (Found : C, 89.5; H, 10.3. $C_{16}H_{22}$ requires C, 89.7; H, 10.3%).

The other *spiro* hydrocarbons similarly prepared are given in Tables 4 and 5.

1-Carboxy cyclopentane-1-acetic acid (17.2 g) on bromination⁵ (PCl_5 , 45.8 g; Br_2 , 17.6 g) gave 1-carboxycyclopentane-1- α -bromoacetic acid, m.p. 135° (lit m.p. 135°) (21 g; 83.7%). Alkaline hydrolysis of this furnished 1-carboxy cyclopentane-1-glycollic acid (15 g.) m.p. 125° (lit. m.p. 125°) (8.5 g; 75.4%). Alkaline potassium permanganate oxidation of the above acid under different conditions⁵ gave 1-carboxy cyclopentane-1-glyoxalic acid, m.p. 133° (lit. m.p. 133°) and 1-carboxy cyclopentane-1,1-dicarboxylic acid, m.p. 190° (lit. m.p. 190°) in yields of 75.8 and 59.5% respectively.

References

1. A. KANDIAH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1215.
2. S. C. SEN GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 389; 1939, 16, 349; 1940, 17, 101, 183.
3. D. N. CHATTERJEE and S. R. CHAKRAVARTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 507.
4. L. F. FIESER and R. G. KENNELLY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1611.
5. J. M. SAGAR and G. S. SAHARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 35, 133; H. S. BAJAJ, R. D. DESAI, J. M. SAGAR and G. S. SAHARIA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 624.
6. G. S. SAHARIA and B. R. SHARMA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 480.
7. C. C. PRICE, W. Y. CHEN and R. J. CONVERY, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 2301.